

Analysis on the Good and Dark Sides of Social Media in Era 4.0

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ABSTRACT

This article explores a discourse on the light and dark side of social media, derived from a variety of studies. It also provides a reflection on the subject. The article uses literature review as a research method to make sense of the collected data. In short, social media is neither beneficial nor harmful; it is not neutral. It is just a support to all that we want to convey. Thus, the light and dark side of social networks can be traced back to how a particular individual uses the platform. It simply becomes beneficial or annoying depending on the user himself. Factors such as, but not limited to, intention, prudence, use and self-control contribute to outcomes, whether positive or negative in nature

INTRODUCTION

In the era of digitalization and globalization, often referred to as Era 4.0 or the Fourth Industrial Revolution, social media has indeed become an integral part of many people's lives (Yuniani, Ardianty, & Rahmadani, 2019). They are used for a variety of purposes, the most common of which are interaction and entertainment. For many people, Facebook, Tiktok, Instagram, Youtube and Twitter are an essential part of social networking. The sites have become popular and prominent among people of all ages, genders and races, with hundreds of millions of members. According to a recent study, the reach of social media covers much of the world and includes more than Facebook, Twitter, blogs, YouTube and Flickr. (Solis, as cited in Dickey & Lewis, 2010). So how will the digital world change the entire world? Now it's in full swing. We generate a lot of data every year through our Facebook posts and hundreds and thousands of Google searches every minute and also through using Google Maps to find directions to the desired destination. Social media has transformed the way information and news are disseminated. Users can access a wide range of news sources, follow influential figures, and engage with trending topics. Social media platforms serve as a platform for news sharing, citizen journalism, and real-time updates. This accessibility to information has both positive and negative implications, as it requires critical thinking to navigate through the abundance of information and combat misinformation. A concise definition of social media emphasizing the technology behind it - social media is a series of Internet-based applications that extend the conceptual and technological roots of Web 2.0, while allowing the production and sharing of user-generated content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Therefore, in this context, it refers to an upgraded version of an original website.

Corollary to this, Web 2.0 is concerned with a platform in which information and applications are no longer developed and published by people, but are instead continually amended by all users in a participatory and collaborative manner (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Some define social media as platforms where users may build a site with personal information to communicate with friends both literally and online, allowing them to find individuals with similar interests (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011). According to this techno-biological description, social media helps individuals network and communicate information, which may either develop or destroy connections.

In the broadest sense, social networking sites can be defined as: Web services allow individuals to (1) create public or semi-public profiles in a limited system, (2) make lists of other users with whom they communicate, and (3) also view and browse through their list of links like what is done by others in the system. The structure and terminology of these relationships may vary from place to place (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Similarly, a social media ecosystem is a collection of social networks (user-generated content, blogs, audio, video, music, news, photography, and tweets) that collaborate with technical technology number (Safko & Brake, 2009). The heart of a social networking site is its user community. The users are at the core of any social networking platform, as they are the ones who create profiles, connect with others, share

content, and engage in conversations and interactions (Trusov, Bucklin, & Pauwels, 2009). Social media has a definitive history that began in the 1970s (Monica, 2016). Arpanet, which stands for Advanced Research Projects Agency Network, was one of the earliest computer networks and is considered a precursor to the modern internet. It was created by the United States Department of Defense's Advanced Research Projects Agency (ARPA) in the late 1960s (Fouad, 2018). Users of the nascent Internet formed small, tight-knit communities of highly skilled users (Kiehne, 2004). As a result, ARPANET heralded in the first social media.

LITERATURE RIVIEW

Social media is now ubiquitous and widely used around the world. Social media is a key motivator for consumers to go online, according to research (Global System for Mobile Communications, 2015). Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Tumblr, Tiktok and Instagram are some popular examples. Participation in online social networks has grown exponentially in recent years (Acquisti & Gross, 2006). The systemic and dynamic aspects of social media play a significant role in shaping its nature and impact on individuals and society. These aspects encompass various dimensions, including technological, social, and cultural elements. According to Seltzer and Mitrook, social media appears to encourage ongoing dialogue between creators and users, making them more interactive in nature than standard websites (in Dickey & Lewis, 2010). Social media allows individuals to connect and communicate with people from different parts of the world. It provides a platform to maintain relationships with friends, family, colleagues, and acquaintances, regardless of geographical distance. Additionally, social media facilitates the formation of new connections and communities based on shared interests, hobbies, or professional networks.

METHODS

This study uses a literature review as research approach to make sense of the data acquired. Because, a literature review can be used as a research approach to make sense of the acquired data (Evans & Kowanko, 2000), literature reviews are increasingly being employed to handle the accumulation of information associated with social media. The vast amount of data generated on social media platforms presents a challenge in understanding and analyzing the information effectively. As assessments, rather than original research, are increasingly used as the basis for multiple selections, it is essential that they be performed (Evans & Kowanko, 2000). This is intended to assist readers in shedding light on the positive and negative aspects of social networking sites.

RESULTS

This section is thematically divided, a priori, into two parts: (1) the good side of social networks; and (2) the dark side of social media. Dividing the section thematically into the bright side and dark side of social media is a valid approach to exploring the different aspects and

effects of social media. This division allows for a comprehensive examination of the positive and negative impacts that social media can have on individuals and society.

The good side of social networks

Social media enables people from different geographical locations to connect and communicate effortlessly. It breaks down barriers of distance and allows individuals to engage in conversations, share experiences, and build relationships with people from diverse backgrounds and cultures. Social media, the internet that connects people around the world, is a blessing to the modern world and has now become an inevitable aspect of society (Aishwarya & Vinod, 2017). Indeed, social media has become deeply integrated into our communities and daily lives to the point where its removal would significantly impede the flow and exchanges of communication.

Figure. 1 Esensial Digital Headlines In 2022

(<https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2022-global-overview-report>)

Furthermore, the transition from traditional forms of communication to a horizontal communication network model structured around the Internet and wireless communication has initiated a multitude of communication models from the roots of cultural change. fundamentalization, when virtual becomes an important principle in our reality (Castells, 2010). As a consequence, Social media platforms provide opportunities for individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds to interact, share their traditions, and celebrate their heritage. It promotes cross-cultural understanding and fosters appreciation for different perspectives, languages, customs, and art forms. Social media enables cultural exchange on a global scale, enriching communities with diverse cultural influences. It has become crucial to our sense of living in a social world in a psychological sense (Couldry, 2012). It must be acknowledged that media has become a part of our lives and has an impact on them.

According to Seltzer and Mitroo (2007), the architectural and communicative characteristics of social media seem to foster active conversations between authors and their readers, making them more conversational than traditional websites, system and thus offers greater relationship-building potential. Following this idea, relationships with individuals can be further developed through social media. In addition, it has allowed an individual to interact with hundreds, if not many others, about the products or companies that provide them (Mangold & Faulds, 2009), as a result, people will no longer need to go to a particular store or place to chat, purchase materials, and seek feedback about the company that provides them.

Online social networks have revolutionized how people connect and communicate. They have eliminated barriers of time and distance, allowing individuals to connect with friends, family, colleagues, and like-minded individuals from across the globe. This enhanced connectivity fosters collaboration, knowledge sharing, and cooperation on a scale never seen before (Cheung, Chiu, & Lee, 2011). The rise of online social networks has transformed cooperation and communication by breaking down geographical barriers, enabling global collaboration, empowering individuals, facilitating community engagement, and democratizing access to information and resources.

This new era of connectivity has brought about tremendous opportunities for cooperation, innovation, and positive social change. Social media platforms have a global presence, allowing people from various locations to connect and engage. It breaks down geographical boundaries, making it possible for individuals to communicate with others who may be in a different country or continent. This global reach fosters cross-cultural understanding and collaboration. Through online platforms, people can work together, share resources, and contribute their skills and expertise, bridging the geographical gaps that may have otherwise hindered collaboration.

Social media platforms can enhance communication and engagement among employees in the public sector. It provides a channel for sharing information, updates, and announcements in a timely and accessible manner. Employees can feel more connected and informed, leading to higher job satisfaction. (Khan, Swar, and Lee, 2014); travelers can use social media platforms to gather information about their desired destinations. They can search for travel blogs, read reviews and recommendations, and explore user-generated content related to specific locations. Social media provides real-life experiences and insights from fellow travelers, helping

individuals make informed decisions about their travel plans. (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010); have the potential to reinforce civic engagement by empowering individuals to participate in civic activities, express their opinions, and mobilize for social and political causes (de Ziga, Jung, & Valenzuela, 2012), (Abdillah, & Leon, 2014); social media platforms have the potential to increase buyer-seller relationships by facilitating direct communication, enhancing brand engagement, and fostering customer trust and loyalty. (Sashi, 2012); boost social capital by facilitating connections, fostering social interactions, and enabling the exchange of information and resources among individuals (Ellison, Steinfield, & Lampe, 2007); and Social media has the potential to drive innovation within organizations by fostering collaboration, facilitating knowledge sharing, and providing platforms for idea generation and feedback (Tsai, 2001).

The Dark Side of Social Media

On the other hand, social media may have a detrimental impact. For example, social media platforms strengthen social networks while eroding individual relationships (Bala, as cited in Aishwarya & Vinod, 2017). This is supported by Booth's study (as described in Keller, 2013), which found that people are becoming more sociable and engaging with others, but the form of that communication has changed so that individuals are not meeting face-to-face as frequently as they are accustomed to.

This assumption implies that individuals expanded their engagement, albeit in a mediated manner. As a consequence, social media is eroding personal and offline relationships. According to Berlinger (as cited in Chasombat, 2014), virtual life experiences can cause hallucinations to the value of human interaction as a necessity for bodily, psychological, and social wellbeing.

Furthermore, youths regard social media as a cause of mood and anxiety disorders for certain adolescents, a platform for cyberbullying, and a source of addiction (O'Reilly, Dogra, Whiteman, Hughes, Eruyar, & Reilly, 2018). Social media use has resulted in negative results for the individual user, such as an increase in despair and loneliness, as well as neglect of existing close relationships, according to the study (Kraut, as cited in Newham, 2012). As a result, social media promotes unpleasant feelings, which might lead to disease or disorder.

The immersive structure and content features of social media, such as the strong peer presence and exchange of a plethora of visual images, imply that social media, working through negative social evaluations, transportation, and peer socially constructed processes, can strongly impact body image issues (Perloff, 2014). Social media can sometimes

contribute to negative social judgment and comparisons, leading to feelings of inferiority among some individuals. People may feel envious of others' accomplishments, possessions, or experiences, which can lead to a sense of inferiority. Comparisons based on selective information can contribute to negative social judgment and self-doubt. This hateful verdict obtained through social media has allowed people to act violently, even at the expense of their health, such as the fear of gaining weight. In a nutshell, social media convinces individuals to look perfect at all costs. The rise of teenage hackers who hack on banks to steal money, destroy government systems, threaten dams slander someone cyber bullying (Jamilah, Astutik C, & Asiah K, 2020) .

Figure 2. Cyber Bullying

(<https://www.comparitech.com/internet-providers/cyberbullying-statistics/>)

Furthermore, a group of researchers found that there is a statistically significant negative association between the time students spend on social networking sites and their academic success (Paul, Baker, & Cochran, 2012). Due to the negative correlation, social networks have a negative impact on student learning outcomes; that's because social networking sites act as entertainment for them. Students also exhibit addictive behavior, in which they use social media even in class, which disrupts other students and causes them to have problems concentrating (Çolak, 2014).

Students obsessive behavior on social networking sites is certainly making them look down on. Students may have difficulty concentrating in class and may be sleep deprived. According to the study, especially

compared with people who rarely check social media before going to bed, those who check social media most often before going to bed are about 1 percent more likely to have a sleep disorder, 5 times (Levenson, Shensa, Sidani, Colditz, & Primack, 2017).

Facebook, according to Vaidhyanathan (2018), is a machine that would disperse propaganda to huge numbers of people, distract them from crucial matters, stimulate hatred and bigotry, weaken social trust, subvert respectable journalism, encourage doubts about science, and participate in massive surveillance all at the same time. This is supported by Allcott and Gentzkow (2017)'s study, which found that people are considerably more inclined to trust reports on social media, especially if they have ideologically separated social media networks. People's prejudice and narrow-mindedness are exacerbated by social media, which can lead to violence. These tensions are worsened by social media fake news.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Social media has intertwined itself in the social context. It has become institutionalized in the society, entered lives of most people, and changed human interactions and connections. Without a doubt, it has radically transformed the world. It offers several advantages, majorly it aids people to communicate and to get updated. However, it also provides disadvantages such as distraction and addiction.

To concretize, an example of which must be given. Social media makes one isolated tending to focus all day long scrolling his newsfeed; he becomes mentally absent in the actual social context, since he is too absorbed on the parcels of information that interest him. On the other hand, one may utilize social media to become more connected to his friends, especially to those who are far from the actual social setting. Social media, in this case, acts as an instrument to bridge him between and among people. It makes people both isolated in a physical sense and connected in a digital context, at the same time.

In reality, social media is not beneficial nor malevolent; it is neither neutral. It is only a medium of whatever one wants to convey. Therefore, the bright and dark sides of social media can be traced upon on how a specific individual uses the platform. It just becomes beneficial or untoward depending on the user himself. Factors, such as, but not limited to, intention, caution, usage, and self-control, contribute to outcome—positive or negative. Indeed, the human intervention dictates and provides color on the effects one may receive on the consumption of social media.

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